

Disease brief Crimean Congo Hemorrhagic fever (CCHF)

	Characteristics	Description
1	Disease and Pathogen	<p>Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever (CCHF) is a tick-borne viral disease. CCHF virus (CCHFV) belongs to the genus <i>Orthonairovirus</i> (family <i>Nairoviridae</i>, order <i>Bunyavirales</i>).</p> <p>Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever virus (CCHFV) in humans is transmitted by bites from infected ticks (mainly of the <i>Hyalomma</i> genus) or by direct contact with blood or tissues of infected ticks, viraemic patients or viraemic livestock. The disease is characterised by a sudden onset of flu-like symptoms, photophobia, abdominal pain, diarrhea and vomiting. Haemorrhagic manifestations can be present in severe cases. Few patients may present mood swings, confusion and aggression. The case fatality rate is approximately 30% among hospitalised patients. In Europe reports have so far been restricted to the Balkan region, Spain, Russia and Turkey (1; 2)</p>
2	Regulatory status in the EU	<p>CCHF in humans is a notifiable disease at the EU/EEA level.</p> <p>CCHF is included in Dir 2003/99/EC (in Annex I -point B – “List of zoonoses and zoonotic agents to be monitored according to the epidemiological situation”)</p> <p>CCHF is a WOA- notifiable disease.</p> <p>CCHFV is considered by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a priority pathogen for research and development.</p>
3	Geographical distribution (of autochthonous cases)	<p>CCHF is the most widespread viral tick-transmitted hemorrhagic fever. CCHF is endemic in all of Africa, the Balkans, the Middle East and in Asia.</p> <p>In the EU/EEA and its neighboring countries, sporadic cases and/or outbreaks of CCHF have been reported in Albania, Bulgaria, Georgia, Greece, Kosovo, Russia, Spain, Ukraine and Turkey.</p> <p>Detailed information on CCHF cases that have occurred in the EU/EEA since 2013 is available. (2; 3)</p> <p>There are reported studies on the influence of climate variables on the incidence of Crimean Congo Haemorrhagic Fever (CCHF). It is important to note that <i>Hyalomma</i> ticks prefer warm and dry climates and evidence for a relation between increasing populations of these ticks and climate change has been provided for some countries (8; 10) .</p>

4	Reservoir / main host	<p><i>Hyalomma</i> ticks (mainly <i>H. marginatum</i>, <i>H. anatolicum</i>, <i>H. rufipes</i> and <i>H. asiaticum</i>) are competent CCHFV vectors and reservoirs.</p> <p>The principal tick vector in Europe is <i>H. marginatum</i>.</p> <p><i>H. lusitanicum</i> ticks seem to play an important role in virus circulation in Spain.</p> <p>CCHFV is transmitted among ticks transstadially, transovarially and venereally, while transmission by co-feeding may also occur. After infection, ticks remain infective for their whole life. (4)</p>
5	Host range / susceptible species (domestic / wild)	<p>Wild and domestic animals are susceptible to CCHFV infection and serve as hosts for the virus, such as cattle, sheep and goats. Migratory birds may be important for introduction of the virus into new areas by carrying infected ticks. Many bird species are not susceptible, but some species may act as a vehicle for spreading CCHFV between co-feeding ticks (WOAH Terr. Code).</p>
6	Vector-borne transmission	<p>The principal vectors of CCHFV are <i>Hyalomma ticks</i> (mainly <i>H. marginatum</i>, <i>H. anatolicum</i>, <i>H. rufipes</i> and <i>H. asiaticum</i>).</p> <p>The principal tick vector in Europe is <i>H. marginatum</i>.</p> <p>CCHFV circulates in nature between <i>Hyalomma</i> ticks and vertebrate hosts.</p>
7	Environmental transmission	<p>No.</p>
8	(Main) transmission routes to domestic animals	<p>Ticks, during blood feeding.</p>
9	(Main) transmission routes to humans	<p>CCHFV is transmitted to humans by bites from infected ticks or by direct contact with blood or tissues of infected ticks or viremic livestock tissues during and immediately post-slaughter of animals. There have been a few reports of infection after drinking unpasteurised milk or after consumption of raw meat from freshly slaughtered livestock.</p> <p>Hospital-acquired infections can occur due to direct contact with blood or tissues of viremic patients or improperly sterilized medical devices.</p>
10	Disease indicators	

11	a) Clinical signs	Many wild and domestic animal species are susceptible to CCHFV infection, but they do not develop clinical signs. In experimental infections, mild general clinical disease has been observed.
12	b) Seroconversion	When infected, animals become viremic for approximately 2–15 days, allowing the tick-animal-tick cycle to continue when another tick bites. Animals seroconvert after infection.
13	c) Other disease indicators	No.
14	Indicators relevant for monitoring (Indicator-based surveillance)	Indicator-based surveillance based on clinical signs is not possible due to lack of production and clinical signs in animals.
15	Test systems available for infection/disease detection	<p>The methods currently used in the diagnosis of CCHF are:</p> <p><u>Virus isolation:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - through intracranial or intraperitoneal inoculation of newborn mice, using blood samples from acute phase patients or ticks homogenized. - on cell lines - RT-PCR <p>RT-PCR testing has long turn-around time (2–5 days) and requires a high infrastructure laboratory. A more flexible approach is needed (9).</p> <p>Samples: serum or plasma samples collected during the febrile or viraemic stage of infection, or from liver of infected animals.</p> <p><u>Serological tests:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indirect immunofluorescence test - IgG-sandwich and IgM-capture ELISA. <p>Samples: serum or plasma samples.</p>

		<p>Several commercial assays for PCR and serology are available but currently, there are no 'gold standard' or widely available and approved assays for the serological detection of CCHF in animal samples.</p> <p>The diagnosis of human CCHF may be confirmed by directly detecting the presence of CCHFV or by measurement of serological responses consistent with acute infection.</p> <p>There is currently (2022) no WOA Reference Laboratory for Crimean–Congo hemorrhagic fever. (6)</p>
16	Surveillance component options (+ rationale)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Serological surveillance of domestic ruminants in high-risk areas 2. Serological surveillance of wild ruminant in high-risk areas 3. Pathogen detection in ticks collected from domestic ruminants in high-risk regions 4. Pathogen detection in ticks collected from wild ruminants in high-risk regions 5. Pathogen detection in ticks collected from migratory birds in high-risk areas and seasons 6. Surveillance of ticks in areas at risk of introduction and establishment of the vector <p>1. Domestic ruminants are important indicators of the presence of disease in an area. Serological surveys (probability-based) are needed because of the lack of typical clinical signs. 2. Experience from Spain shows that wild ungulates are good indicators of infection being present in an area. Seroprevalence in specific populations was as high as 88% (15) 3. and 4. Collecting ticks from slaughtered and hunted ruminants is a convenient method to assess presence of virus in vectors. 5. While birds generally are not important for the transmission cycle of the disease, they migrate over long distances, and can thus introduce infected ticks into areas formerly free from the disease. 6. <i>Hyalomma marginatum</i> is present in Southern Europe, but absent from Northern European countries (5). Due to climate change, expansion of the infected ticks to previously free areas in Europe in the future seems likely.</p>

		GENERAL POPULATION	EXPOSED	INFECTED	INFECTIOUS	SYMPTOMATIC	GP/VD/VISIT	DEAD	Component name	
VECTOR-borne diseases										
Crimean Congo Hemorrhagic Fever (CCHF)	Ruminants								Serological surveillance of domestic ruminants in high-risk areas	
	Wild ruminants								Serological surveillance of wild ruminant in high-risk areas	
	Hare								No surveillance component specifically designed	
	Hyalomma marginatum									Pathogen detection in ticks collected from <i>domestic</i> ruminants in high-risk regions
										Pathogen detection in ticks collected from <i>wild ruminants</i> in high-risk regions
										Pathogen detection in ticks collected from <i>migratory birds</i> in high-risk areas and seasons
										Surveillance of ticks in areas at <i>risk of introduction</i> and establishment of the vector
Human								Surveillance components targetting human were not in scope		
17	Comparison of surveillance component options (main advantages/disadvantages)	Seroconversion in animals is a good indicator of CCHFV prevalence. As infected animals are usually asymptomatic, only active surveillance will reveal CCHFV circulation. Serological surveillance is challenged by a lack of serodiagnostic tests suitable for large-scale animal testing, no clear guidance for standardized surveillance of CCHFV in the animal health sector, and the cost of routine implementation (9). PCR or antigen detection in ticks is a good option for early detection of virus introduction. Collecting ticks from animals is more cost-effective than active sampling of <i>Hyalomma</i> ticks from the environment. Ticks can be pooled for diagnostic testing. In addition to virus detection in ticks, vector abundance should be monitored to identify areas of risk for establishment of virus.								
18	Countries which already carry out surveillance for this pathogen	Routine reservoir/host monitoring is not broadly implemented. All EU/EEA countries have passive surveillance in humans implemented.								
19	References	1) https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/crimean-congo-haemorrhagic-fever/facts/factsheet 2) https://www.who.int/health-topics/crimean-congo-haemorrhagic-fever#tab=tab_1								

- 3) <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/crimean-congo-haemorrhagic-fever/surveillance/cases-eu-since-2013>
- 4) <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/tick-surveillance-effort-2015-2019>
- 5) <https://ecdc.europa.eu/en/disease-vectors/surveillance-and-disease-data/tick-maps>
- 6) <https://www.woah.org/en/what-we-offer/expertise-network/reference-laboratories/#ui-id-3>
- 7) https://www.woah.org/fileadmin/Home/eng/Health_standards/tahm/3.01.05_CCHF.pdf
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- 13) <https://animal-diseases.efsa.europa.eu/CCHFV>
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		15) Sánchez-Seco, M. P., Sierra, M. J., Estrada-Peña, A., Valcárcel, F., Molina, R., de Arellano, E. R., ... & Negrodo, A. (2022). Widespread detection of multiple strains of Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever virus in ticks, Spain. <i>Emerging Infectious Diseases</i> , 28(2), 394.
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